

DEVELOPMENT OF NECESSARY PROFESSIONAL SKILLS IN FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *Today, the socio-psychological need to create a system of motivational approaches and relationships to future physical education teachers is increasing. The model of creative approach to the work of future physical education teachers is used in Great Britain, USA, Australia, Finland, South Korea, Czech Republic, and Latvia. In these countries, the innovative activities of physical education teachers will make it possible to identify existing problems and achievements in establishing psychological relations with students, and plan to improve the quality of education.*

Keywords: *Motive, development, person, idea, thought, need, factor.*

Today, Uzbekistan's bold step towards a new revival requires further improvement in the socio-economic, political, cultural and educational spheres. In this way, profound reforms are being implemented in health care, science, culture, technology, economy, education, physical education and sports and other areas. In particular, it is important to improve the scientific potential and professional training of future teachers in the field of sports. Also, it is necessary that the professional training of future physical education teachers should take the main place, along with the development of competence, along with the transformation of subject-related skills and qualifications into personal improvement. Therefore, a modern future teacher of physical education should have professional knowledge, personal qualities, including general culture, general professionalism, coaching and wellness activities, as well as professional training in the form of organization, management and research. is supposed to have a set.

New psychological approaches to the training of future physical education teachers can be conditionally divided into two models.

The model of creative approach to the work of future physical education teachers is used in Great Britain, USA, Australia, Finland, South Korea, Czech Republic, and Latvia. In these countries, the innovative activities of physical education teachers will make it possible to identify existing problems and achievements in establishing psychological relations with students, and plan to improve the quality of education.

Today, the socio-psychological need to create a system of motivational approaches and relationships to future physical education teachers is increasing. This makes it an urgent task to improve the system of training and training them as personnel. In this sense, there is a need to train future physical education students on the basis of modern students, to develop their professional knowledge and skills, and to prepare them for psychological innovative activities based on a creative approach.

Gibson emphasized that the student should be psychologically ready for professional activity, so that he should be an advanced, productive creative person, with wide-ranging interests, rich in the business world, and open to editorial innovation. Professional activity consists of

psychologically motivational, technological and reflexive parts. This process is carried out in two directions: formation of professional preparation for perception of innovation and teaching to act innovatively. Knowledge activity of students and its management are of special importance in the organization of professional activity.

According to J.Simons, as a result of the professional activity of the physical education teacher, students' physical fitness, individual-psychological characteristics, their motives are studied and trained in detail, methodical complexes are created that provide a continuous didactic system for physical training in activities outside the school and auditorium. ; various competitions, educational events promoting a healthy lifestyle: conversations, parties, sport-shows are organized, students' interests in sport types are taken into account, they are attracted to sport circles, physical, mental and intellectual abilities of students are developed; the educational and psychological environment in the family, class and school is studied in detail and their cooperation is developed.

According to Z.Bauman, the goal of preparing future physical education teachers for professional activity is to form the student's desire for innovation, the ability to work independently, using modern psychological technologies, interactive methods, and extracurricular activities. Since it is to improve the qualification of conducting classes, the physical education teacher should demonstrate the following skills in professional activity.

- uses creative motivation in classes, evaluates professional activity;
- cooperates in creative interaction of students;
- organizes work with determination, responsibility and honesty;
- determines the need for professional activity;
- prepares for involvement in creative activities;
- aligns personal goals with psychological activity, etc.

According to A.S. Rooney, modern psychology is motivational in developing the professional knowledge and skills of future physical education teachers, instilling in them a new worldview and thinking, and in improving the quality and efficiency of physical education, in being able to use their professional competence at a high level. using the approach, aims to create motivational activity and achieve social changes on this basis.

In our opinion, the formation of professional motivation is an important factor. When teachers approach their profession with interest and enthusiasm, they can work effectively in the educational process. The development of professional motivation helps the teacher to feel successful in his profession. Teaching students and improving their health requires a motivational approach. A teacher can be more successful by properly planning his activities and taking into account the individual characteristics of students. Professional motivation ensures the development of not only knowledge, but also personal and moral qualities. This allows the teacher to ensure long-term effectiveness in the educational process.

Physical education is not only a process consisting of pure sport competitions, but also the development of moral and willful qualities in young people through this education. During the performance of physical exercises, young people develop willpower, speed, agility, endurance, their health is strengthened, work skills, mental activity are increased, moral standards such as courage, honesty, determination, independence are developed, steps are taken towards maturity.

One of the urgent tasks is to motivate future physical education teachers to become skilled masters of their profession, to start professional activities, and to direct their work motives to the efficiency of professional activities.

Motivation is the process of movement of motives, a set of motives that urge a person to the main activity. When translated from French, the vowel kush means reason.

H.Heckhausen developed the principles of motivation. According to the first principle, intrinsically motivated behavior is not aimed at satisfying physical needs, such as hunger, hunger, and pain. The work carried out in this direction, the scientists noted, revealed that these needs do not serve to restore the disturbed homeostasis of the body. However, in external behavior, they can be corrected, and motivated behavior is interpreted as aimless activity.

Y. Klinger calls the activity of the game as an aimless directed action based on interactive motivation.

According to R.White, the greatest activities of an individual in the process of interaction with the environment are called mobility motivation. Mark Rujnes, an American scientist, agrees with this opinion and considers the initial steps of the activity to be intensive, and the steps close to the result to be extensive.

1. The motivation of an activity consists of both intrinsically and extrinsically motivated behavior.

2. This or that behavior is considered a motivation to maintain some optimal level of activity or to keep it in a ready state.

In the formation of motivation for extreme sports in future physical education teachers, the motivation factor for achieving success in their professional activities is of high importance.

At the beginning of the last century, D.S.McClelland developed the Thematic Arrertsertiv Test (TAT) methodology, aimed at determining the differences in the occurrence of individual quality changes of success motivation. He identified two types of success motivation: motivation to achieve success and motivation to avoid failure. Later, this method was modified by H.Heckhausen, W.Mayer, L.Kemmler.

In our opinion, physical education teachers should have developed leadership skills. Leadership skills allow students to feel free and confident in the learning process. Physical education teachers should be able to manage the social environment in the classroom and motivate students. A teacher with strong leadership skills understands the needs of each student and approaches them individually. Through this ability, the teacher teaches students not only physical exercises, but also discipline and cooperation. The main task of leadership is to strengthen the collective spirit and establish mutually trusting relationships. Leadership ability is important in effective organization of teacher's activities.

H.Heckhausen defines the nature of interdependence of active activity and success motivation at the most important level and shows three important motivational vectors:

Individual subjective perception of the probability of success and difficulty of the task before the individual;

The subject's level of importance of this task, as well as the desire to support and increase self-esteem;

A person's tendency to adequately attribute success and failure and responsibility to himself, other people and the situation. Therefore, the role of these vectors in creating motivation for the necessary professional feelings in future physical education teachers is considered high. Identifying the psychological factors and developing the editorial bases of their solution are urgent tasks for today's higher education.

Within the framework of the dissertation, it is necessary to take into account their activity and educational stress when directing future physical education teachers to motivational activities based on innovative psychological approaches.

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